

VULNERABILITY TO VIABILITY
GLOBAL PARTNERSHIP

Observed Environmental, Social, and Economic Responses in Chilika Lagoon

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V2V Working Paper Series

V2V Global Partnership “Working Paper Series” aims to facilitate the exchange of ideas, mobilize knowledge, and generate broad-based discussions on vulnerability-viability themes within the context of small-scale fisheries. The Working Paper Series will provide a collaborative and interactive platform for academics, practitioners, representatives of civil society, and individuals interested in making written contributions to the theoretical, methodological, practical, and policy aspects of small-scale fisheries, both locally and globally. To contribute to the V2V Working Paper Series, please contact v2vglobalpartnership@gmail.com.

Reflections from Chilika - V2V Field School

Small-scale fisheries (SSF) are important social-ecological systems across all parts of the world. Strongly anchored in local communities, SSFs reflect a way of life, and they provide critical contributions. Yet, their efforts and their existence are often overlooked as many SSF communities remain economically and politically marginalized, are highly vulnerable to change, and remain invisible in policy debates. Nonetheless, the continuity of many SSFs suggests certain strengths and forms of resilience. A holistic understanding of what causes vulnerability, as well as what makes fisheries social-ecological systems viable and through what processes is required. This understanding needs to be place-based and situated within the SSF context, and the processes surrounding it must be long-term, collaborative and iterative.

The Chilika - V2V Field School aims to provide a creative platform for graduate students and early career scholars and practitioners to deliberate and learn about concepts, approaches and methods helpful to achieving transitions from vulnerability to viability within SSF social-ecological systems. The Field School takes place every year in the Chilika Lagoon, Bay of Bengal, India, where participants gain firsthand experience and creatively engage in furthering their understanding and knowledge of vulnerability to viability transitions, and experiment with concepts and approaches that are novel, transdisciplinary and problem oriented. The Reflections from Chilika - V2V Field School is part of the V2V Working Paper Series that exclusively focuses on documenting the main learnings, insights, reflections gained by the Chilika - V2V Field School participants during their weeklong journey with the fisher communities of Chilika Lagoon.

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Observed Environmental, Social, and Economic Responses in Chilika Lagoon

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Abstract

This paper reflects on the experiential learning gained through participation in the Chilika–V2V Field School (August 2025), which explored environmental, social, and economic responses of communities living around the Chilika Lagoon in Odisha, India. Over eight days of site visits, discussions, and community workshops, our group observed how diverse coastal and lagoon-based communities navigate and adapt to shifting ecological, economic, and social conditions. Key experiences included engaging with fishing villages undergoing livelihood transitions, conservation groups transforming poaching into eco-tourism, relocated coastal residents confronting sea-level rise and erosion, and forest-dependent communities strengthening collective land rights. Our reflections underscore resilience as a dynamic and continuous process rooted in collective action, cultural identity, and pragmatic strategies. We analyzed community responses through the three pillars of sustainability—environmental, social, and economic—while recognizing their strong interdependence in shaping community viability and wellbeing. This experiential learning approach deepened our understanding of resilience, wellbeing, and happiness as interconnected concepts shaped by community agency and knowledge. Beyond academic insights, the field school emphasized humility, deep listening, and respect for community-led solutions. The experience generated practical lessons relevant to development practice, policy engagement, and efforts to foster sustainable and inclusive community resilience.

Keywords Experiential learning • Community resilience • Sustainable livelihoods • Collective action • Community wellbeing • Socio-ecological systems • Chilika Lagoon

1. Introduction

1.1 Setting the Stage

This paper examines the intertwined concepts of *happiness*, *well-being*, and *resilience* in the context of community viability, drawing on experiential learning from a week-long field course in the Chilika region of Odisha, India. Chilika Lagoon, located on the eastern coast of India, is the largest brackish water lagoon in Asia and an internationally significant Ramsar site (Jayaraman et al., 2007; Mishra & Jena, 2015). It

harbours remarkable biodiversity, including more than 400 vertebrate species, the second-largest seagrass meadows in India, and serves as a habitat for over one million migratory birds. The ecosystem faces serious pressures from sedimentation, pollution, eutrophication, invasive weeds, and the impacts of climate change, which have reduced fisheries productivity and triggered social conflicts (Acharyya, Raulo, et al., 2023; Kadekodi & Nayampalli, 2003; Rath & Adhikary, 2008). Since 2000, restoration programs - including the opening of a new lagoon mouth - have successfully enhanced salinity levels, improved biological productivity, and restored fishery resources, positioning Chilika as a model of adaptive wetland management (Acharyya, Sudarsan, et al., 2023; Pattnaik & Kumar, 2018). Socio-economically, the lagoon supports the livelihoods of local fishing communities, yet continues to grapple with challenges such as population growth, pollution, and climate change. Ensuring its sustainability requires adaptive governance, ecological monitoring, and effective mitigation of environmental pressures to maintain both ecological balance and community well-being (Ray, 2021).

These ecological and socio-economic dynamics provided a rich context for experiential learning, enabling students to connect theory with practice and reflect on how resilience and viability are shaped at the community level. Experiential learning bridges theory and practice, enhancing both technical and soft skills such as problem-solving, communication, and teamwork (Desai et al., 2018; Tar Lim et al., 2024). This approach also motivates students, deepens their understanding, and better prepares them for the workplace. By observing and reflecting on the various site and community visits conducted around Chilika Lagoon, our group sought to understand and summarize how various stakeholders are adapting to changing circumstances to ensure their short and long-term viability.

Our field experience took place from August 9-16, 2025, bringing together a diverse group of students and researchers from across India, Indonesia, and Canada. Over the course of the week, we engaged in presentations, site visits, and community interactions - ranging from fishing villages and fish markets to wetland conservation areas, bird sanctuaries, and coastal communities impacted by erosion. These encounters, complemented by significant discussions with local leaders, community members, and field school facilitators, formed the basis of our reflections. Although our exposure to communities was limited in time and depth, and our interactions were both directly and indirectly related to resilience, we gathered a diverse set of perspectives and narratives, revealing both visible and invisible forms of responses and adaptations to change.

This paper therefore aims to share insights from the field course, reflect on the outcomes of experiential learning for students and researchers, and contribute to a broader understanding of how community responses - shaped by happiness, well-being, and resilience - play a vital role in sustaining community viability.

1.2 Clarifying Our Meaning and Definitions

To guide our reflections and analysis, we first clarify the meaning of the core concept – viability, happiness, well-being and resilience- that frame our understanding throughout this paper. In V2V, vulnerability and viability are intertwined. The driving principle of all our interactions relied on understanding how communities viewed their own **viability**, which we defined as:

Viability is closely tied to the happiness and well-being of a community. Resilience—defined below as the ability to cope, adapt, and transform—is the driving force that ultimately sustains a community’s viability.

For the purposes of this paper, we also defined a **response** as:

A response is any apparent or desired reaction of humans or environmental outcomes driven by

ecological, social or economic changes, which in turn can influence individual and collective happiness and well-being.

Other important definitions that guided our field observations are:

- **Happiness:** the experience of joy, contentment, or positive well-being, combined with a sense that one's life is good, meaningful, and worthwhile (Greater Good Science Center, n.d.)
- **Wellbeing:** is a multifaceted and complex concept that encompasses various dimensions of an individual's life. It is closely related to health and quality of life, existing within both subjective and objective dimensions. Subjective well-being involves personal life experiences and feelings, while objective well-being includes the comparison of life circumstances with social norms and values (Sfeatcu et al., 2014)
- **Resilience:** Resilience refers to the ability to successfully adapt to stressors, maintaining psychological well-being in the face of adversity. It's the ability to "bounce back" from difficult experiences. Resilience is not a trait that people either have or don't have. It involves behaviors, thoughts, and actions that can be learned and developed in everyone. (U.S Department of State, n.d.)

1.3. Connecting Our Definitions

These concepts are deeply connected: resilience supports the preservation and restoration of wellbeing, while wellbeing fosters conditions for happiness to flourish. In Chilika, where communities are shaped by environmental change, shifting economic conditions, and evolving social dynamics, linking these concepts provides a valuable lens for assessing viability.

As a group, we agreed to count a broad range of responses, accepting any verbal accounts, observed practices, or tangible outcomes that demonstrate coping, adaptation, or transformation.

2. Field School Experiences, Excursions, and Observed Responses

2.1 General Location Overview of Excursions and Visits

In mid-August 2025, our field school unfolded along the shores of Chilika Lagoon in Odisha, India - which is a vast, shifting body of brackish water that sustains fishing livelihoods, supports migratory bird populations, and shapes the rhythms of nearby villages. Over the course of six days, we engaged in excursions to fishing communities, conservation areas, markets, beaches, and forests, speaking with and hearing directly from local community members about the ways they respond to environmental change, economic pressures, and social challenges. The stories shared with us were all layered with history, resilience, and examples of pragmatic responses or adaptation. We recorded these response stories and photographed our observations to ensure proper identification and recognition.

Across the week, the communities we visited described their "responses" not as a one-time shift but as an ongoing process - adjusting livelihoods, enforcing social norms, protecting resources, and asserting governance rights as conditions changed. These stories were not simply accounts of survival; they reflected deliberate, often collective choices grounded in local knowledge and place-based values. Observing these responses, and the settings in which they took shape, underscored the inseparability of people, environment, and economy in Chilika's future.

Figure 1*Field School Location Map in the Chilika Lagoon Area*

Sources: Created by Poonam (2025)

2.2 Daily Excursions, Visits, and Observed Responses

This section describes every activity our group conducted during the field course as well as the concrete responses that we observed every day. This is intended to summarize our observations and provide the content needed for the conceptualization section.

2.2.1 Day 1 - Arrival and Framing the Journey

Day 1 began with a warm welcome to Chilika from community members, who greeted us with a mix of ceremony and informality, speaking about the deep connections between Chilika Lagoon and the people who live around it. This was not just an opening event - it was a framing moment for the week. Local hosts and field school organizers encouraged us as field school participants to approach the coming days with humility, to “unlearn” preconceived protectionist ideas, to listen more than we spoke, and to see beyond single-issue narratives.

No local visits or excursions were carried out, and no responses or observations were recorded on this day.

2.2.2 Day 2 – Barkul Fishing Village

The day opened with morning sessions setting the stage for field course participants to consider different meanings of reflection and resilience. The theme that our team was assigned to explore over the week was “responses”. In the afternoon, we visited Barkul fishing village, where we were warmly welcomed and were able to walk through the village. While there, women from a self-help group welcomed us into a shaded gathering space and sat with us to speak openly about life in the village. They also shared more with us about the decline in fishing livelihoods due to reduced fish stocks and profitability.

Figure 2

Women’s self-help groups (SFGs)

Source: The photo was captured during the Chilika - V2V Field School 2025 by HIRAK JYOTI SARMAH

Here, responses were shaped by profound livelihood changes. Due to declining fish stocks, fishing - once the backbone of the community - was no longer seen as a viable profession. Many families discouraged their children from pursuing fishing; some young men noted that their parents refused to teach them how to fish. Instead, villagers turned to alternative livelihoods - such as tourism, micro-businesses, wage labour, or migration to cities.

Socially, women’s self-help groups (SFGs) became vital. These SHGs pooled savings to offer loans, mediated domestic conflicts before they reached legal action, and enforced community norms such as preventing child marriage. They also accessed government funds to expand micro-businesses, enabling repayment and eligibility for larger loans. The community’s sense of response in these groups also extends beyond economics. From their perspective, the “response” was not just about income; it was about sustaining social cohesion under pressure. They took action to create social safety nets when fishing alone could not.

2.2.3 Day 3 - Mangalajodi Wetland Conservation

Day 3 took us on a guided boat visit to Mangalajodi Wetland Conservation, a village at the northern edge of Chilika Lagoon. Once a heavily poached area, Mangalajodi Wetland is now a haven for migratory birds. As we travelled through narrow channels, local guides recounted how the community dramatically shifted from poaching to conservation in the 1990s after a respected conservationist leader - a local “nature expert” - persuaded the most influential hunters to take oaths at the village temple to abandon poaching.

Figure 3

Ecotourism in Mangalajodi reflects the harmony between nature and people

Source: The photo was captured during the Chilika - V2V Field School 2025 by Franco Soli

The guides spoke with pride about their current actions, which have contributed to the increased bird diversity and the revival of ecological balance. Changes were due to the ethics and morals of villagers that didn't agree with the poaching mentality, which demonstrated the power of community and social values.

As the ban on poaching movement gained momentum, villages shared that the transformation from poaching to conservation required coordinated efforts, involving multiple stakeholders. The first step was convincing the poachers to change their lifestyle by emphasizing the social, economic and environmental benefits of this transition. Driven by important social and cultural values, traditional poachers were asked by the “nature expert” to make an oath at the Kalijai Temple to amplify their commitment to the new lifestyle.

The ban on poaching also had social impacts, as it required villagers to respond to this change by shifting lifestyles. One social response we observed is that villagers are putting an emphasis on teaching their children conservation values so that they can grow into this profession as well.

The ban on poaching also opened the door for the community to respond to new economic opportunities such as developing a conservation and birdwatching economy within their village, which led to the creation

of equitable employment opportunities for both men and women as tour guides. The guides spoke with pride about the increased bird diversity and the revival of ecological balance which generates income for their community while protecting the very ecosystems that sustain them. Environmentally, we visibly observed the responses that the guides simultaneously communicated to us, which were rebounded bird biodiversity.

2.2.4 Day 4 - Nalabana Bird Sanctuary, Kalijai Temple, and Balugaon Fish Market

On Day 4, we were taken to three different locations. In the morning, we were invited to visit the Nalabana Bird Sanctuary, managed by the wildlife agency and the Odisha government. This is a core conservation zone where officers described their approach of minimal human interference, intervening only when necessary. The sanctuary is located far from residential areas, isolated, and strictly guarded by the government. Furthermore, fishermen are prohibited from fishing in the conservation area. Only those with permits are allowed to enter the area. Furthermore, visitors are prohibited from taking photographs at the site. Waste management protocols to minimize ecological impacts, the use of watchtowers to allow uninterrupted community observation, and even plans to adopt AI cameras to more quickly detect intruders. Officers educate local residents on awareness and impose sanctions on those who violate the rules. This is done in response to preserving the naturally formed bird habitat without destructive human activities, so that the birds can enjoy their natural habitat and preserve their species. However, this has also led to an economic impact, as fishermen have had to convert fishing grounds into conservation areas.

Figure 4

Group photo with the management team of Nalabana (Nalaban) Bird Sanctuary, as field school participants were not permitted to take photographs inside the sanctuary area

Source: The photo was captured during the Chilika - V2V Field School 2025 by V2V

In the afternoon, we visited the Kalijai Temple, where former poachers once took a vow to renounce hunting. This sacred response combines ecology and spirituality, transforming hunting into conservation through symbolic accountability.

Figure 5

Kalijai Temple rises gracefully by the Chilika waters, where prayers mingle with the sea breeze and colours reflect the harmony of faith and nature

Source: The photo was captured during the Chilika - V2V Field School 2025 by Franco Soli

In the afternoon, we visited the Balugaon Central Fish Market. There, we witnessed the interaction between fish sellers and buyers. Many stalls sold fish sourced from local fishermen (Chilika fishermen), dominated by men. Only a few women were seen working in the market, cutting fish, sorting fish, and knitting. Women knitted and sold the fish because they perceived a decline in demand for fish cutting. They did this as a response to maintain their income. Furthermore, we saw technological changes employed by wholesalers, including the use of ice to keep fish fresh for resale and the use of transportation to expand their market reach. This location demonstrates the fishermen's response to sustaining their livelihoods by selling their produce to wholesalers. Wholesalers are using technology to maximize profits. This also highlights the role of women who work at the market to earn extra income for their families.

2.2.5 Day 5 - Old Podampetta Beach and Purunabandha

On Day 5, we visited Old Podampetta Beach, where the shoreline had allegedly retreated under the force of human (e.g. sand mining) and natural interventions (e.g. cyclones). Standing on eroded ground, a community leader described the loss of homes and community relocation, as well as the uncertain nesting patterns of Olive Ridley turtles. Later in Purunabandha, community leaders gathered with us at Maa Gangadevi Temple to explain the challenges they are facing, and the solutions they are applying in reaction to encroachment and erosion threats. They also spoke to the physical actions they are taking to protect the environment and their livelihood.

On this day, we observed intertwined human and environmental responses, emphasized by stories of disruptions and adaptations driven by environmental changes. As one example, we heard that the government's response in 2015 to eroding landscapes was to relocate villagers from Old Podampetta (which

was ocean front) to New Podampetta (which was in land). Villagers at Podambandha also showed us detailed GPS and GIS maps created to document their shared commons. They explained that these maps could be used to defend their claims in case of legal disputes or further erosion. In another example, community leaders shared with us how they are responding to environmental threats in the canals by reactively advocating against destructive fixed gear in these areas. As a final example of responses to ecological threats, community members shared they have planted mangroves to stabilize banks and banned harmful fishing practices.

Figure 5

At Old Podampetta, the eroding shore and scattered debris whisper stories of time, tides, and human neglect against the restless sea

Source: The photo was captured during the Chilika - V2V Field School 2025 by Ika Suciati

An upcoming social response gaining momentum is creating awareness and education to promote more fish-based diets e.g., in schools for children. We heard this is motivated by the beneficial health effects of fish diets but also to create a sustainable demand for local fish.

One economic response we heard related to withstanding declining fishing productivity, some villagers responded by shifting into alternative professions - such as construction, daily wage labour, and other

alternative livelihoods. This has led to wellbeing changes as we heard these new activities have impacted the culture of the village and brought different economic opportunities and challenges.

2.2.6 Day 6 - Uparadikiri Village and Community Forest

Day 6 saw us at Uparadikiri Village Community Forest in Nayagarh District, where members of the Kondh community described their journey to secure legal rights to 590 acres of forest under the Forest Rights Act. We were greeted with a warm and joyful welcome by the community, with rangoli, welcome music, warm greetings, and delicious food.

Figure 6

A warm welcome from the forest guardian community

Source: The photo was captured during the Chilika - V2V Field School 2025 by Franco Soli

Local community members invited us and guided us to explore the forest they have long protected. We observed how the community appears to live simply and off the land, relying on a well for their water and

intertwining with local domesticated plants and animals. We also observed minimal technology in the village, and an overall serene and tranquil atmosphere.

In response to the geographical distance between the village itself and public facilities like hospitals and schools, we heard from them that they rely primarily on the forest for all their needs, e.g., herbal gardens from the forest for their healing.

Figure 7

Forest guardian heroes (Uparadikiri villagers)

Source: The photo was captured during the Chilika - V2V Field School 2025 by Franco Soli

To protect the forest and prevent illegal logging, we heard the community has implemented logging restrictions, seasonal quotas, and rotating forest patrols carried out by community members. They also impose penalties for violators.

To ensure forest sustainability, they also assign distinct roles to women and men. They are also investing in resilience for future generations: establishing a local primary school, developing a health-promoting medicinal garden, and ensuring that every household contributes to forest protection through collaborative forest patrol rotations between all community members/neighbours.

2.2.7 Day 7 - Group Discussions and Reflections

Day 7 began with a flag raising ceremony for Indian Independence Day. Afterwards, our group spent most of the day in reflection, processing all the stories we had heard and the observations we had captured about community responses. This day was vital for our group to organize all the responses we had gathered into conceptualizations described below.

No field excursions or visits were carried out on this day.

2.2.8 Day 8 - Community Policy Workshop

On Day 8, the community members we met over the course of the week were invited to join us for a shared workshop, during which our field course groups presented our observations. This gathering served both as a culminating moment of collective reflection and as a platform for community voices to contribute to our narrative.

Before the presentations, we also heard final reflections from local community members, who shared additional stories of their experiences living in balance with Chilika Lagoon and the growing challenges they face.

One villager from Purunabandha summed up a deeper sentiment by sharing: “There is no happiness. And there is no sadness. There is simply the reality of the situation.”

We also heard that tenure is important. Villagers explained that without secure rights to access and use the lagoon, they cannot plan or sustain their livelihoods. Economic displacement, they warned, is not simply forced removal - it is erosion of access, spiralling into loss of control over land and water. They emphasized that meaningful tenure is not just legal protection; it is the foundation for community resilience and reestablishing future harmony with Chilika.

A villager from Purunabandha village highlighted how the fishers who are encroaching are non-fishers and come from castes that are non-fishing castes. These non-fishers are profit-driven, and don't bring fishing knowledge. They also don't understand or respect the delicate aquatic, environmental, and social links that allow Chilika to remain in balance. So, the actual fisher-caste, who have fished in Chilika for decades, are forced to only catch smaller fish and under sourced fishlings, e.g., to supply the aquacultures which are degrading Chilika lagoon, and putting the historical actual fishers' livelihoods at risk. To capture the steady decline in fish stocks and the threat posed by outsiders unfamiliar with Chilika's delicate systems, an older villager representative shared: *“I used to catch thousands of fish a day. Now it is hard to even catch ten.”*

Participants also spoke of internal pressures, and how they are not defeated. They continue to mobilize, protest, and advocate - even in the absence of leadership since the passing of Krishna Chandra Jena, a respected local organizer. They said that sense of ownership, agency, and a say in their future is all vital to reclaiming their role in shaping Chilika lagoon's (and their) future.

Though sobering, the messages heard on this last day of the field course were not of resignation. The community expressed deep gratitude for our presence and the chance to have their stories heard more widely. They made clear that their struggle is ongoing - and that this is a story of reclaiming rights and endurance in the face of powerful external forces. The community's resolve, they said, remains.

The field course workshop ended with group presentations, lively discussions, and a joint community-shared lunch on site.

3. Conceptualization and Abstract Interpretations

The figure shows variables as we have observed, that lead various responses in a structure towards happiness and well-being for community resilience.

Figure 8

Conceptual structure

Since we currently have a working definition for responses, we will now delve into the conceptualizations part of it and as such we must now think about where we have picked up the categories and ideas of our divisions.

We have taken the social, economic and environmental categories from the three Pillars of sustainability for our conceptual structure.

Expanding on why we specifically landed on the 'Conceptual Structure' diagram, we found through our observations and experiences on the various excursions that the variables we have noted down in the diagram itself are all interconnected and as such, to put this interconnection into a working format and to draw lines between all of them, this diagram has come up as the focal point in our reflections on what a response is in the context of this paper.

To help solidify the core concepts behind each of these categorizations, here is an expansion on each of them on them:

- **Environmental Response:** For the sake of our paper, by our previous definition for a response, we may define Environmental responses as changes that occur in the ecology or environment driven by either natural or manmade factors.
- **Social Response:** If an environmental response is a change that occurs in the ecology or environment, we may define a social response as any change that occurs in the context of a community or group of human beings, irrespective of the factors affecting it.
- **Economic Response:** Any sort of change affecting the economic or financial state of individuals or communities that comes up due to any factor.

Now, since we have properly defined what each of the categories of our conceptual structure actually mean, we may now talk about the variables we associate with them. As our model uses all these variables as interconnected threads, it would be remiss of us to not properly elaborate as such.

The connections are bidirectional. This shows a feedback loop: a positive change in one area (e.g., a strong social response such as collective action) can lead to a positive change in another (e.g., a better economic outcome such as a new livelihood), increasing the community's overall happiness and resilience. The opposite is also true: a negative change (such as an external intervention) can have an impact on all three pillars and community well-being.

According to our conceptual structure, variables that fall into one response category may also fall into another. For example, we saw social migration in response to livelihood loss. This might be considered both an economic and cultural response. Alternatively, forest restoration in villages like Uparadikiri could be considered an environmental or social response.

3.1 Social Response and Viability

3.1.1 Collective Actions

Across all the villages we visited, we noticed that people are collective in their response to the crisis. For example, in the Barkul village near the Chilika Lagoon, people are united and fighting against the Garuda Boat House legally (external interventions), whereas in Uparadikiri village, people are united and engaged to claim Individual Forest Rights (IFR) and Community Forest Resource Rights (CFR) under the Forest Rights Act of 2006. And in Mangaljodi village, former bird poachers have taken a collective oath at the Kalijai temple to preserve bird species and safeguard ecosystems. This collective process demonstrates community resilience and people's viability in nature.

3.1.2 Government Interference

We saw in response to environmental decline; the forest department has established the Nalabana Bird Sanctuary inside the Chilika lagoon. Declared under the Wildlife Protection Act (WLPA), 1972, this protected area serves as a haven, allowing the lagoon's diverse bird populations to flourish. The sanctuary's preservation efforts have played a crucial role in safeguarding the rich bird habitats and, in turn, ensuring the overall health and well-being of the entire ecosystem.

On the other hand, the Nalabana Bird Sanctuary once served as the traditional fishing grounds for six to seven nearby fishing villages. With its declaration as a protected area, fishing activities inside the sanctuary have been strictly restricted, cutting off local communities from this vital resource base. In response, some villagers continue to enter the sanctuary discreetly at night to lay their nets, attempting to sustain their livelihoods despite the prohibitions. These actions, however, often result in confrontations with the Forest Department, leading to fines, penalties, and in certain cases, the seizure of boats.

3.1.3 Market Access

We witnessed the Balugaon fish market - a vibrant place that provides a vital source of livelihood for various fish dependent communities. It's a central meeting point where vendors, traders, buyers, and daily wage workers come together, all of whom rely on the fish for their survival. The market's success is directly linked to the well-being of these people, as their ability to make a living and support their families is entirely dependent on its operation.

At the same time, the market is not just a social institution, but also a dynamic economic system that develops and maintains local livelihoods. It contributes to economic viability by facilitating flows of income, strengthening local micro-economies, and creating opportunities that extend beyond the immediate trading space. Importantly, the Balugaon fish market is not static; it is responding to changes brought about by technology and infrastructure advancements. For example, new ice-freezing facilities and transportation technology have enabled fish to be kept for longer periods of time and transported over longer distances. This shift expands the market's geographical reach, connects local traders to regional and even urban markets.

The market is changing in ways that allow it to adapt economically while sustaining the social fabric of the communities that depend on it.

3.1.4 External Institutions and Community Cohesion

We additionally looked at the impact of external institutions on community resilience. One example is that the Uparadikiri community is collaborating with an organization called NIRMAN to aid them in their struggles. This partnership is helping villagers secure their traditional land rights, giving them a stronger sense of ownership over what's theirs. A similar effort is happening in Purunabandha and Podampetta villages, where the Dakshin Foundation is helping people understand their tenure rights within the Coastal Regulation Zone (CRZ). Through community-led commons mapping, the foundation provides people with legal education. This helps them understand their rights and how to protect what belongs to them. This knowledge encourages the community to work together towards conservation.

3.2 Environmental Response and Viability

3.2.1 Restoration efforts

In Mangalajodi village, due to the poachers turning into conservationists, the ecosystem responded by allowing for new bird and plant species. We observed that the Nalabana Bird sanctuary's environment is prospering with bird and fish populations because of ecosystem protection. Uparadikiri villagers have collectively restored numerous plant and tree species in their forest. This results in a viable and healthy environment. In the example of Uparadikiri village restoration, social responses such as people's collective action have resulted in environmental well-being.

3.2.2 Change in fish composition

We heard the fish species have changed since the Chilika lagoon's new sea mouth opened. More saltwater species have started to occupy the lagoon, as shared by the fishers. In addition, they said the jelly fish population has increased, posing a significant threat to fishing because many jelly fish are captured in nets. Fishermen noted that cleaning it has become tough for them.

3.2.3 External interventions

We also observed how external interventions, such as aquaculture in the Chilika lagoon, locally known as *Gheris*, affected the fishermen's traditional fishing grounds. This is also noted to pose a serious threat to the ecosystem, as stated by the people. Another external intervention is the Garuda, a private boat house company that threatens the people's livelihoods as well as the Chilika ecology on which fishers rely.

3.3 Economic Response and Viability

3.3.1 Suboptimal fish catch

We heard from people that there is a decrease in fish catch at all of the places we visited that primarily relied on fisheries for their livelihood. People everywhere told us that fishing is not what it used to be. The fish aren't as plentiful, and their livelihoods are directly impacted. They added this decline is a result of various issues, including changes to the local ecology and environmental damage from different types of degradation. People are responding to these issues with migration and exploring alternative professions as a source of economic livelihood.

3.3.2 Livelihood Shifts

In response to the loss of traditional livelihoods (fishing), we heard that people were migrating to cities like Bhubaneswar, Chennai, Bengaluru, and Calcutta for work. Some people work for a daily wage, such as in construction. Except for Uparadikiri, in all other villages, migration is a common response for financial security. The Balugaon fish market also sees in-migration, with women from surrounding villages coming to do fish cutting jobs. We observed that this creates competition among women. People in Mangalajodi village fish and work as guides in eco-tourism activities, which allows them to make more income. These response to livelihood transitions allows people to become viable.

3.3.3 Additional livelihoods

People in Uparadikiri village are now entitled to community forest rights. People are already collecting minor forest products. They have mango plantations for additional income. They also plan to cultivate bamboo to produce additional revenue for the households.

3.3.4 Conceptualizing Interconnected Responses

The variables and responses in our reflections are deeply interconnected, forming a complex web where a change in one area often triggers a ripple effect across others. This dynamic relationship underscores the central theme of community resilience, which is not built in isolation but through the interaction of social, economic, and environmental factors.

In our field visits we observed all aspects of life are deeply connected in a feedback loop that determines their resilience. A **social response**, like the collective action of villagers in Uparadikiri to restore their forests, directly improves their **environment**, which in turn secures their **economic viability**. Conversely, a negative **environmental change**, such as declining fish populations in Chilika Lake, triggers an **economic crisis** for fishers and leads to **social responses** like migration. Our observations show that a community's well-being is not just about one factor; it's about the entire system working together, where action in one area, whether positive or negative, inevitably affects the others.

4. Conclusions

Our time in Chilika offered a window into how communities continually respond to change in ways that are practical, collective, and deeply rooted in place. The observations we carried with us, especially from the women’s self-help groups in Barkul to the oath-bound conservationists of Mangalajodi, and from the resilience of Podampetta’s relocated villagers to the forest guardians of Uparadikiri, showed us that well-being and happiness are not separate from resilience but are woven together through everyday choices. Each encounter reminded us that resilience is less about “bouncing back” and more about adapting, protecting, and creating new pathways for community life to continue with dignity.

Equally, the field experience demonstrated the power of learning through direct engagement. Walking the villages, listening to stories, and sharing meals created a form of understanding that no classroom could offer. Experiential learning in this context was about observing responses and reflecting on them together, questioning assumptions, and appreciating the complexity of human–environment relationships. It taught us that observation requires humility, patience, and openness to perspectives that challenge our own. Looking ahead, it feels important to continue exploring how external pressures such as tourism, aquaculture, and conservation regulations intersect with local knowledge and rights. There is also value in paying closer attention to how younger generations in Chilika imagine their future, since they will inherit both the challenges and the opportunities of resilience-building.

As a group, this journey left a lasting imprint on us. It sharpened our awareness of how interconnected social, economic, and environmental life is and deepened our respect for community-driven responses. More than anything, it reminded us that growth comes from listening and being present, not from offering solutions. The overall impact of this experience has been a shift in perspective: resilience is not only something we observed in Chilika’s communities, but also something we began to cultivate within ourselves through shared learning and reflection.

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Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Global Partnership

The Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) project is a transdisciplinary global partnership and knowledge network. Our aim is to support the transition of small-scale fisheries (SSF) from vulnerability to viability in Africa and Asia. Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. We use the term viability not just in its economic sense but also to include its social, political, and ecological dimensions.

The V2V partnership brings together approximately 150 people and 70 organizations across six countries in Asia (Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand), six countries in Africa (Ghana, Malawi, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania), Canada and globally. This unique initiative is characterized by diverse cultural and disciplinary perspectives, extensive capacity building and graduate student training activities, and grounded case studies from two regions of the world to show how and when SSF communities can proactively respond to challenges and creatively engage in solutions that build their viability. Further information on the V2V Partnership is available here: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org.

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**VULNERABILITY TO VIABILITY
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